

Delphic Hymns 1 and 2

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The first and second Delphic Hymns were songs found inscribed on the walls of the Treasury of the Athenians at the Sanctuary of Apollo at Delphi. The first hymn survives in 24 lines and the second in 46. The first was composed by Athenaios son of Athenaios and the second by Limenios. The first hymn could date either to 138 or 128 BCE and the second dates to 128 BC. They were meant to be performed during a Pythais (plural Pythaidēs), a festival and procession from Athens to Delphi held at irregular intervals (only when an omen necessitated it). The two hymns are significant because they include musical notation and can be (and have been) performed in modern times.

Date Range: 138 BCE - 128 BCE

Region: The Sanctuary of Apollo at Delphi

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Greece, Aegean, Central Greece, Phokis

The sanctuary's temenos including the stadium further up the slope.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bélis, A. 1992. *Corpus des inscriptions de Delphes. Tome III, Les hymnes à Apollon*. Paris.
- Source 2: Weil, H. 1893. "Nouveaux fragments d'hymnes accompagnés de notes de musique." *Bulletin de correspondance Hellénique* 17:569–583.
- Source 3: Weil, H. 1894. "Un Nouvel Hymn à Apollon." *Bulletin de correspondance Hellénique* 18:345–362.

Notes: Pöhlmann, E. 1970. *Denkmäler altgriechischer Musik; Sammlung, Übertragung und Erläuterung aller Fragmente und Fälschungen*. Nürnberg. Reinach, T. 1893. "La Musique des hymnes de Delphes." *Bulletin de correspondance Hellénique* 17: 584–610.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oeaw.ac.at/kal/agm/>
- Source 1 Description: Recorded performances of the hymns from a symposium organized by the Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.kerylos.fr/>

– Source 2 Description: Ensemble Kerylos produces reconstructions of Greco-Roman music

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

– Chisel

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Stone

Notes: Parian marble

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The text is inscribed on ashlar blocks which were cut and fitted together by stone masons.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: It's not so much "stored" as it is displayed on a wall.

Tomb

– No

Cemetery

– No

- ↳ Temple
 - No
- ↳ Shrine
 - No
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - Yes
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - Yes
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - Yes
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: Treasury

Notes: Treasury of the Athenians at Delphi

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Only religious public space

Notes: The treasury on which the hymns were inscribed is decorated with triglyphs and metopes, which depict the Labours of Theseus and Herakles in relief.

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No
- ↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: NA

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not possible to know the number but as it was displayed on a highly visible building on the Via Sacra of a major Greek sanctuary, the intended audience would have been a big one.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: The text was originally performed at a religious festival but once it was it was inscribed to commemorate the original event, it would have been read, perhaps to be performed as the musical notation was included.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Song of praise to a deity.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: The pythaidēs happen irregularly after specific omens.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is it visible?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it hidden?
 - No
- ↳ Can it be touched?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?
 - No
- ↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve a protective function?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve a healing function?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
 - No
- ↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
 - No
- ↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
 - No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The hymns were 2 of several hymns that would have been inscribed on the wall. A third, more fragmentary hymn survives but not to the same extent.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Hymn

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The first hymn (written by Athenaios) is dedicated to Apollo and it mentions Apollo as a son of Zeus several times. In the beginning, it mentions the Muses as the daughters of Zeus and the brother of Apollo. The second (written by Limenios) includes references to Zeus as well as Artemis (Apollo's sister) and Leto (Apollo's mother).

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarh (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - No
 - ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: NA
 - ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- Notes: This does seem to be the case (e.g. Prometheus' Trick at Mykone, Tantalos' cannibalistic dinner) in mythology but not always.

- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - Yes
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - Yes
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - Yes

- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - Yes
 - Notes: If Zeus can imprison his father, then he too can also be imprisoned. But good luck trying.

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: NA

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - Yes

Notes: Line 18 says that Zeus "declares infallible oracles to all humans".

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: Oracles

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The Giant Tityos is mentioned in the second hymn.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: NA

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: NA

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Both hymns commemorate the defeat of the Gauls who attacked Delphi in 279 BCE. The hymns refer to the event both metaphorically and literally. In the second hymn, Apollo shoots Tityos for his attempted sexual assault on Leto, which Limenios metaphorically connects

with the defeat of the Gauls. The hymn also recounts how Apollo destroyed the Gauls for their sacrilege. Historically, the Gauls were defeated by a freezing thunderstorm which facilitated their defeat by the Greeks, who drove them to the Spercheios Valley where they were slaughtered by the Thessalians and the Malians.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

- ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - Yes
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - No
 - Notes: Not in the text.
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The reward in the text is the protection of the city of Athens by Apollo.
- ↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Notes: The text itself is not meant to be dramatic, tragic, comedic, or epic but as music.

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Notes: The inscriptions were commissioned by Athens.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

- A city-state
- A federation or league

Notes: In addition to the polis of Athens, the Delphic Amphiktyony might have had a say in what the Athenians were allowed/not allowed to include as an inscription on their treasury but probably minimal.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

- An empire

Notes: After Theodosius closed down the pagan sanctuaries of the Roman Empire, the sanctuary of Apollo at Delphi was destroyed and abandoned.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

- No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

- No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

- No

Other forms of welfare?

- No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

- No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

- No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

- No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No